

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№4(4)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 440 sahifa,
22-aprel, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda microteaching metodining tashkiliy asoslari va uni samarali qo'llash mexanizmlari.....	10
Abdiqayumova Malika	
Ijtimoiy pedagogik faoliyatning bolalarning moslashuv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdagi o'rni	14
Abdullayeva Yulduz Qurbon qizi, Xudayberdiyeva Zilola Azamat qizi	
Talabalarning og'zaki nutqini interfaol usullar yordamida rivojlantirish	18
Atamirzayeva Ezoza	
English Language Barriers Among Rural Ecotourism Guides in Uzbekistan	22
Aminova Asilaxon Sobir qizi	
Совершенствование методов обучения студентов эффективному управлению временем на основе тайм-менеджмента.....	25
Уразова М. Б., Абатова У. Б.	
Zamonaviy ta'limda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'rni va samaradorligi	30
Xurramova Dilso'z Baxtiyor qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin asosida ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik ahamiyati.....	33
Gaipova Akjunis Qayratovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda o'zini o'zi tashkil etish tushunchasi va uning pedagogik mohiyati.....	37
Alimov Bekzod Nematovich	
O'qituvchilarning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish tadbirlarini maktab darajasida boshqarishning integratsiyalashgan yondashuvi	41
Ahadova Mushtariybonu Akmal qizi	
Talabalarning tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	48
Xurramova Sanobar Mahmatmurod qizi	
Pedagogical Integration as a Factor of Humanization in Professional Teacher Education	53
Yusupova Mukhabbat Anatolyevna	
Yoshlarda iqtisodiy tafakkur shakllanishida etnik muhitning ta'siri.....	58
Erkinova Sevara Najmiddin qiz	
Innovative Approaches to Teaching English in Higher Education: a Methodological Study	61
Gulsara Khakimova	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda kognitiv faollikni rivojlantirishda neyropedagogika asoslari.....	63
Hikmatova Jamila Fatox qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi aqli zaif bolalarning eshituv idrokini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	68
I. S. Xamrayeva, Nuriddinova Muxayyo Ishxodjayevna	
Badiiy matn asosida nutqiy ko'nikmalar va ijodiy tafakkur integratsiyasini ta'minlash metodikasi	73
Jo'rayeva Sevinch Abdialim qizi	
Etnopedagogik muhitda maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning nutqini rivojlantirish.....	77
Murodova Farangis G'anisherovna	
Malaka oshirish jarayonida muammoga asoslangan o'qitish vositasida MTT tarbiyachilarining 4K ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi	81
Ravshanova Xafiza Komilovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida xalq og'zaki ijodi vositalaridan (ertak, maqol, qo'shiq, afsona, doston va boshqalar) foydalanishning nazariy asoslari, xalqaro va milliy tajribasi	85
Tog'ayeva Munisa Muxammadiyevna	
Akademik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish asosida kelajakdagi o'qituvchining kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	89
Tursunova Elmira Ulug'bekovna, Rayimova Mushtariy Raup qizi	
Sensor integratsiya autizm spektri buzilishi bo'lgan bolalarning xulq-atvor va hissiy holatiga ta'siri.....	91
Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna, Abdullayeva Muslima Shovkat qizi	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	96
<i>Xoshimova Dilobar Kuchkarovna, Nortosheva Dildora Orif qizi, Avazmurodova Mehribon Sharif qizi</i>	
Инновационная методика нравственного воспитания в начальных классах: подход межпредметной интеграции	101
<i>Улугмурадова Шохсанам</i>	
Shaxs o'z-o'zini anglashining ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlari	105
<i>Bobonazarov Oybek Shoyim o'g'li</i>	
Samarqand arxitektura-qurilish instituti va shahar infratuzilmasi rivojlanishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik (1950–1990yy).....	108
<i>Abulqosimova Dildora Asrorovna, O'ralov Sodiqjon</i>	
Tabiatshunoslik darslarida steam yondashuvi asosida ta'limni tashkil etish metodlari	111
<i>Gulnora Narmatova Tojiyevna</i>	
AI-Mediated Coil in Oral English Teacher Education: a Didactic Model for Developing Intercultural Communicative Competence.....	115
<i>Mukhammadiyeva Khalima Saidakhmadovna</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda kasbiy stress jarayonining ijtimoiy psixologik xususiyatlari	119
<i>Xotamova Madinabonu Iloxmon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik mahorat fani asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning refleksiv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	123
<i>Xurramova Mohidil Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Bo'lajak kutubxonachilarda ilm-fanga oid bilimlarni o'zlashtirish malakasini shakllantirish	126
<i>O'rozov Abdurasul Norboyevich</i>	
Методологические подходы к развитию духовно-творческого потенциала детей младшего школьного возраста	130
<i>Хасанова Гулшод Касимовна</i>	
Pedagogik ta'lim transformatsiyasida talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	134
<i>Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna</i>	
O'rta maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda voleybol mashg'ulotlarining psixoemotsional holat va ijtimoiy faollikka ta'siri	138
<i>Xonimqulova Durdona</i>	
Farzandlar tarbiyasida otalik va onalik hissining shakllanishining o'ziga xosligi	141
<i>Tursunboyeva Gavharoy Abdivohid qizi</i>	
O'quv jarayonida raqamli kontent (elektron darslik, multimedia materiallari) yaratish texnologiyalari.....	145
<i>Quvatov Shuxrat Akmurodovich, Rashidov Anvarjon Sharipovich</i>	
Scratch dasturida harflarni vizuallashtirish orqali 1-sinf o'quvchilarining tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish usullarini takomillashtirish.....	150
<i>Normurodova Sadoqat Xoliqulovna</i>	
Vaqtini boshqarish hamda to'g'ri taqsimlashning pedagog hayoti va faoliyatidagi ahamiyati.....	155
<i>Tursunova Nilufar</i>	
Sun'iy intellektning ingliz tili o'qitishdagi roli	159
<i>Burxonova Aziza Ikhtiyorovna, Negova Feruza Sharifovna</i>	
Разработка системы адаптивной генерации контрольных вопросов из учебных материалов на узбекском языке на основе гибридного подхода ИИ и таксономии Блума	162
<i>Бегалиев Жалолиддин Камолитдинович, Маматов Ислонбек Ильесович</i>	
Применение данных беспилотной авиации для обновления картографических данных	168
<i>Хакимов Дониёр Бахтиёр угли, Бурунова Муниса Баходировна</i>	
The Role and Significance of the Acmeological Approach in the Managerial Activity of School Principals.....	172
<i>Normurodova Aziza Zuxriddin qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda tarbiya darslarini samarali tashkil etishga o'rgatish: mazmuni, shakli va metodlari ..	178
<i>Sheraliyeva Nasiba Alimkulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy xulq-atvorni shakllantirishda ota-ona tarbiya uslublarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	184
<i>Ashurova Aziza Erkinovna</i>	

Mintaqaviy sanoat korxonalarining biznes jarayonlarini tahlil qilish va baholashning zamonaviy usullari (BPM, Lean, Six Sigma yondashuvlari misolida)	188
<i>Azimova Maxfuza Rashidovna</i>	
O'zbekistonda turli etnik guruhlarda mehnat motivatsiyasining qiyosiy tahlili.....	193
<i>Erkinova Sevara Najmiddin qizi, Saidakbarova E'zozaxon Muzaffar qizi</i>	
"Geogebra" dasturi yordamida geometriya va matematik analiz kursini o'qitishda vizual tafakkurni rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	196
<i>Fayzullayeva E'zoza O'tkir qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida raqamli transformatsiya texnologiyalarini qo'llashning zarurati.....	200
<i>Musurmanova Shodiya Xolmuratovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari va sun'iy intellekt asosida ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirish.....	204
<i>O'ktamov Madadjon O'ktam o'g'li, Boymurodova Shahzoda Alisher qizi</i>	
Gimnastikada akrobatik mashqlarni rivojlantirish metodikasi	208
<i>Raxmatova Nodira Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Suggestiv metodlar asosida xulqi og'ishgan bolalar uchun tarbiyaviy mashg'ulotlarni loyihalash	212
<i>Shermatova Manzura Ikromjanovna</i>	
Tabaqalashtirilgan yondashuv asosida tayyorlov guruh tarbiyalanuvchilarini maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash ...	216
<i>Sanayeva S. B., Toshqulova Z. U.</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida ekologik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi.....	220
<i>Yaxshiboyeva Nargiza Rustamqulovna</i>	
Понятие искусственного интеллекта в контексте образования и его педагогические функции	224
<i>Каримова Сабина Собировна</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kasbiy barqarorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari....	230
<i>Akramjonova Feruza Akramjonovna</i>	
Demografik yuklama sharoitida maktab pedagogik jamoasini samarali boshqarishning hr-strategiyalari.....	233
<i>Axmadqulova Ozodaxon Hamidullo qizi</i>	
Kasbiy identifikatsiya – shaxsning kasbiy o'zligini shakllantirish omili sifatida	236
<i>Bazarov Xayotbek Ne'matovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida qoraqalpoq xalq ertaklari asosida multimediyali mahsulotlar yaratish samaradorligi.....	240
<i>Bekimbetova Aynagul Amangeldievna, Ollaberganova Mohira</i>	
Odam anatomiyasi va fiziologiyasi darslarida muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali talabalarning ijodiy izlanuvchanligini faollashtirish.....	245
<i>Haydarova Pardaxol Boboqulovna</i>	
Chet el va O'zbekiston tajribasida ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil etishning metodologiyasi	249
<i>Inomova Madina</i>	
Boshlag'ich ta'lim tabiiy fanlarini o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodkorligini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	253
<i>Ismatova Zulayho Asadovna, Avazova Gulnoza Qodirjon qizi</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ekologik tarbiyani shakllantirishning samarali yo'llari	256
<i>Ismatova Zulayho Asadovna, Xamroyeva Ozoda Norbo'ta qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida o'quvchilarning so'z boyligi va nutqiy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	259
<i>Mambetova Lobar Mirzavali qizi, Rajabova Nafisaxon Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Kasbiy faoliyatda pedagogik improvizatsiya ijodiy kompetensiya sifatida	264
<i>Miraxmedova Dilafro'zxon Nurilloxon qizi, Jo'rayeva Gulshodaxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Media savodxonlik tushunchasi va uning pedagogik ta'limdagi ahamiyati.....	267
<i>Salomova Lobar Sobir qizi</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida estetik tarbiyani shakllantirish metodikasi	271
<i>Tursunova Malika Baxtiyor qizi, Aminova Oltinay Davranbek qizi</i>	
STEAM texnologiyasi asosida o'quvchilarning ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi	274
<i>Xaydarova Dilafuz Abdukurim qizi</i>	

Refleksiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish – bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash bosqichi sifatida.....	279
<i>Jo'rayeva Maftuna Dilshodbek qizi</i>	
Chimyon–Chorvoq kurort-rekreatsiya zonasidagi rekreatsiya obyektlari va ulardan foydalanish holati	283
<i>Djurayeva Lobar Vaxitovna</i>	
G'ovlar osha yuguruvchi qizlarning maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini oshirish asosida sport musobaqalariga tayyorlash.....	286
<i>Sattorqulova Fotima Jamol qizi, Sattorqulova Zuhra Jamol qizi</i>	
Grammatika va yozuv ko'nikmasining integratsiyalashuvini ESL o'quvchilarning grammatik ravonligini o'stirishdagi ahamiyati	292
<i>Ne'matova Iroda Ilhom qizi, Karimova Xadicha Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Формирование экологической культуры и проектных компетенций молодежи в формате хакатона “Климатон–25”	295
<i>Бегмуратова Зоя Асаматдиновна</i>	
Portlovchi kuch sifatini rivojlantirishning nazariy va metodik asoslari.....	298
<i>Xushvaqtov Shaxzod Mamatqul o'g'li</i>	
Enhancing the Writing Skills of Non-Philological Students Through Artificial Intelligence Tools	302
<i>Rajabova Rakhimakhon Maksudovna</i>	
Supporting Children With Autism in Inclusive Education: Effectiveness of Multisensory, Visual Scheduling, and ABA Approaches.....	306
<i>Safarova Sanobar Omontashevna, Rakhimova Ozoda Abdurasul qizi</i>	
O'quv topshiriqlari orqali 6-sinf o'quvchilarining pragmatik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi leksik birliklar bilan ishlashning ahamiyati	310
<i>Ashirbayeva Nafisa Aminbayevna</i>	
O'smirlarda nevrotik holatlarning namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari va ularni diagnostika qilishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari	313
<i>Abduraximov Doniyor Abdusaid o'g'li</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'rgatishda talabalarning ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish metodlari.....	317
<i>Abirqulova Nafisa Abdusalamovna</i>	
Yuqori sinf ingliz tili darslarida tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodik modeli	321
<i>Ahmadjonova Diyoraxon Dilshod qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlarini innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida tashkil etish va pedagogik muloqot madaniyati	326
<i>Alimov Shavkatbek Shuxratbekovich</i>	
Identification and Systematization of Emotional Intelligence Indicators in Pre-Service Primary School Teachers.....	330
<i>Aminova Nasiba Davlatboy kizi</i>	
Oligofren bolalarda kognitiv jarayonlarni rivojlantirishda o'yin terapiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari va pedagogik samaradorligi	334
<i>Amirsaidova Sh. M., Jumanazarova Mashhura San'atbek qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darslarida matn ustida ishlash metodikasi	339
<i>Asilbekova Shoxsanam To'liqin qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda olimpiya harakatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	344
<i>Axmadaiyeva Gulnoz Ikramovna</i>	
Zamonaviy tibbiyotda hissiyotlarni boshqarishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	348
<i>Azgarova Gulsum Alisher qizi</i>	
The Use of Problem-Based Learning Methods in Delivering High-Quality Education in Schools	351
<i>Bekmuratova U'mit Ken'esbay qizi, Abdiev Azamat</i>	
Akseleratsiyaning o'quvchilar xulq-atvoriga ta'siri	355
<i>Botirova Oydina Vadimovna</i>	
Ta'limda zamonaviy pedagogik innovatsiyalar va raqamli transformatsiya: bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashning metodologik asoslari	361
<i>Eshimova Nasiba Zohiddin qizi</i>	

Kasbiy samaradorlikni oshirishda sun'iy intellektning roli: "KasbNavigator" platformasi misolida	365
<i>Isayeva Oylarxon Ro'zimatjon qizi, Sobirov Muslimjon Muxsinjon o'g'li</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan maktablarda o'quvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatini rivojlantirish: integratsiyalashgan ta'lim va ijodiy yondashuv.....	369
<i>Mavlanova Saidaxon Umarovna</i>	
Yoshlar orasida ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning depressiv holatlarga ta'siri	373
<i>Mirzaxmatova Sayyora Saydaxmatovna</i>	
Kiberijtimoiylashuv sharoitida avlodlararo kommunikativ o'zaro ta'sirning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	375
<i>Muhiddinova Mamlakat Nabi qizi</i>	
"Emotsional Learning Analytics"metodi asosida o'qituvchilarning reflektiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish ...	380
<i>Omonqulova Diyora Farhod qizi</i>	
Talabalarda milliy identiklikni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	384
<i>Qudratov Davron Sami o'g'li</i>	
Media kompetentlik va media savodxonlik tushunchalarining ilmiy-pedagogik mohiyati, tarkibi va rivojlanish tarixi.....	388
<i>Rahimova Xosiyat Uralovna</i>	
Yangilanayotgan O'zbekistonda tarix fani oqituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy va metodik asoslari	392
<i>Raxmatova Ondagul Oybek qizi</i>	
Talabalarining kasbiy tayyorgarligida mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik muamolari.....	395
<i>Raxmonova Mavluda Suvon qizi</i>	
O'smirlarni kiberbulling tahdididan himoya qilishning psixologik mexanizmlari	398
<i>Sattorova Mohinur Sherali qizi</i>	
Bolalarda oilaga hurmat va qadriyatli munosabatni rivojlantirish jarayonida ota-ona bilan hamkorlik qilish yo'llari	401
<i>Sharofutdinova Nigora Kenja qizi, Usarova Marg'uba Nazar qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirishning vertikal modeli: tizimli tahlil va cheklovlar	405
<i>Toxirova Nafisa Dilshod qizi</i>	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda maxsus ehtiyojli o'quvchilar uchun texnologiyalar va tajribalarning roli	409
<i>Tursunov Alisher Isoqovich, G'ulomov Davlatbek Istat o'g'li</i>	
MTTda qadriyatlar kompetentligini rivojlantirish vositalari	412
<i>Urinova Rushana Tursunniyozovna, Usarova Marg'uba Nazar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda nutq o'stirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	415
<i>Xakimova Xosiyat Jurayevna</i>	
O'smirlik davrida deviant xulq-atvor namoyon bo'lishining psixologik xususiyatlari	419
<i>Xalilova Sarvinoz Qodirali qizi</i>	
Ta'lim platformalarida mustaqil ta'lim ma'lumotlarini relyatsion model asosida optimallashtirish	422
<i>Xasanov Baxrom Boktiboyevich</i>	
Применение информационных технологий для интеллектуального анализа чрезвычайных ситуаций на основе edge computing и компьютерного зрения.....	426
<i>Мамаражабов Музаффар Абдурасулович, Маматов Ислombек Ильесович</i>	
Индивидуальное интеллектуальное развитие личности – как педагогическая проблема	432
<i>Олтибоева Камола Шарофжон қизи</i>	
Представления о реальной и виртуальной дружбе у подростков	436
<i>Хамидова Нигора Илхомовна</i>	

THE USE OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING METHODS IN DELIVERING HIGH-QUALITY EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS

Bekmuratova U'mit Ken'esbay qizi

2nd year of Master's degree, Nukus state pedagogical institute
 named after Ajiniyaz (Republic of Karakalpakstan, Nukus)

Abdiev Azamat

PhD, doc., Nukus state pedagogical institute
 named after Ajiniyaz (Republic of Karakalpakstan, Nukus)

Abstract: The present article examines problem-based learning as a pedagogical model with the aim of fostering independent, critical, and creative thinking among learners. The theoretical foundations of the approach are described, as are its historical development and methodological underpinnings. The ideas of Socrates, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, and John Dewey are also discussed. It is demonstrated that problem-based learning is contingent on heuristic techniques and involves the organisation of relatively autonomous exploratory activity. During this activity, students encounter contradictions, formulate problems, carry out purposeful cognitive exploration, and develop logically sound solutions. The pedagogical conditions for effectiveness are highlighted, namely: high subject-specific and methodological competence on the part of the teacher, clear formulation of objectives and assessment criteria, and the use of modern pedagogical technologies and ICT. The advantages (stimulation of intellectual and practical activity, development of analytical and creative skills) and limitations of the method (demanding requirements regarding students' level of preparation, significant time expenditure) are described, and the combination of problem-based learning with other forms of teaching, as well as the didactic regulation of its application, are recommended.

Key words: problem-based learning, heuristic methods, critical thinking, independent cognitive activity, pedagogical competence, didactic conditions, creative thinking, educational technologies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada muammoli o'qitish o'quvchilarda mustaqil, tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan pedagogik model sifatida tahlil qilinadi. Yondashuvning nazariy asoslari, uning tarixiy rivojlanishi va metodologik negizlari bayon etiladi. Shuningdek, Sokrat, Jan-Jak Russo va Jon Dyui g'oyalari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Muammoli o'qitish evristik usullarga asoslanishi hamda nisbatan mustaqil tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etishni nazarda tutishi ko'rsatib beriladi. Ushbu faoliyat jarayonida o'quvchilar qarama-qarshiliklarga duch keladi, muammolarni shakllantiradi, maqsadga yo'naltirilgan bilish izlanishlarini olib boradi va mantiqan asoslangan yechimlar ishlab chiqadi. Samaradorlikning pedagogik shartlari ajratib ko'rsatiladi, ya'ni: o'qituvchining yuqori darajadagi predmet va metodik kompetentligi, maqsadlar va baholash mezonlarining aniq belgilanishi hamda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va AKTdan foydalanish. Metodning afzalliklari (intellektual va amaliy faollikni rag'batlantirish, tahliliy va ijodiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish) va cheklovlari (o'quvchilarning tayyorgarlik darajasiga yuqori talablar, katta vaqt sarfi) tavsiflanadi, shuningdek, muammoli o'qitishni boshqa ta'lim shakllari bilan uyg'unlashtirish hamda uning qo'llanilishini didaktik jihatdan tartibga solish tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: muammoli o'qitish, evristik usullar, tanqidiy fikrlash, mustaqil bilish faoliyati, pedagogik kompetentlik, didaktik shartlar, ijodiy fikrlash, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается проблемное обучение как педагогическая модель, направленная на развитие самостоятельного, критического и творческого мышления обучающихся. Описываются теоретические основы подхода, его историческое развитие и методологические предпосылки. Также рассматриваются идеи Сократа, Жан-Жака Руссо и Джона Дьюи. Показано, что проблемное обучение основано на эвристических методах и предполагает организацию относительно самостоятельной исследовательской деятельности. В ходе этой деятельности учащиеся сталкиваются с противоречиями, формулируют проблемы, осуществляют целенаправленный познавательный поиск и вырабатывают логически обоснованные решения. Выделены педагогические условия эффективности, а именно: высокий уровень предметной и методической компетентности преподавателя, чёткая формулировка целей и критериев оценки, а также использование современных педагогических технологий и ИКТ. Описаны преимущества (стимулирование интеллектуальной и практической активности, развитие аналитических и творческих навыков) и ограничения метода (высокие требования к уровню подготовки обучающихся, значительные временные затраты), а также рекомендуется сочетание проблемного обучения с другими формами обучения и дидактическое регулирование его применения.

Ключевые слова: проблемное обучение, эвристические методы, критическое мышление, самостоятельная познавательная деятельность, педагогическая компетентность, дидактические условия, творческое мышление, образовательные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

The education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been designed to provide extensive and diverse opportunities for the education of young people. Innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process in preschool, general education, and higher education institutions, as well as the introduction of modern teaching methods, have been shown to have a positive impact on the content and quality of education. It is envisaged that lessons will be organised using a variety of modern teaching techniques and information and communication technologies in accordance with didactic requirements. The integration of problem-based learning techniques within the pedagogy of social sciences and humanities has been demonstrated to enhance the efficacy of learning while simultaneously cultivating students' capacity for independent and critical thinking. In the context of organising independent work, the role of the teacher is pivotal. The teacher is responsible for clearly articulating the objectives, proposing a methodology for completion, recommending relevant reading materials, determining the form and organisation of the work, and establishing deadlines and assessment criteria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is evident that within the context of lessons, pupils acquire a fundamental corpus of knowledge. Nevertheless, it is imperative to recognise the significance of systematic independent study for the long-term retention of this knowledge. The fundamental objective is to transition from a conventional teaching paradigm to one that emphasises the cultivation of pupils' autonomous learning capabilities. The social imperative for enhancing the quality and efficacy of education necessitates that educators employ effective educational technologies. The quest for models that nurture the evolution of critical and productive thinking has given rise to problem-based learning, a pedagogical approach underpinned by heuristic techniques. These techniques are defined as specialised methods designed to uncover novel insights. The objective of this approach is to cultivate heuristic skills in resolving problem situations of both a practical and applied nature and a theoretical and cognitive nature. The integration of learners into exploratory activities has been demonstrated to facilitate the activation of their existing knowledge and analytical skills.

Even Socrates, in his dialogues, cultivated the ability to reason logically and seek the truth through reasoning. The eminent French philosopher J.-J. Rousseau is widely credited with pioneering the concept of learning situations designed to stimulate students' independent cognitive exploration. The educators of the 19th century (I. G. Pestalozzi, A. Diesterweg, and others) sought to ensure that learners not only received ready-made information but also actively sought it themselves. The full theoretical and methodological development of problem-based learning took place in the 20th century, particularly in the works of John Dewey, who criticised the rote-learning school system that provided pupils with ready-made knowledge and underestimated their capacity for active engagement. Dewey proposed a model in which the teacher organises learners' activities so that they solve emerging problems while simultaneously acquiring the necessary knowledge, learning to formulate tasks, seek solutions, and apply the results obtained. This approach was later termed "learning by doing" and subsequently "learning through inquiry". The notion of learning as an investigative activity was further elaborated by the American psychologist J. S. Bruner and other scholars, including I. Ya. Lerner, T. V. Kudryavtsev, A. M. Matyushkin, and M. I. Makhmutov.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Problem-based learning can be defined as a pedagogical approach in which the educator organises autonomous exploratory activities for the learner. For learners, the ability to think independently and critically, as well as to make informed decisions, is of critical importance. The primary objective of education is not the accumulation of facts but the development of practical competencies essential for future professional endeavours. It is imperative to acknowledge the pivotal role of constructive interaction between educators and students in fostering effective learning environments. The cultivation of students' confidence in their own learning activities, complemented by the use of contemporary pedagogical technologies, contributes significantly to positive educational outcomes. In the contemporary educational environment, the role of the teacher has evolved to include organising the learning process in a way that fosters not only reproductive thinking but also creative thinking among students. In a market-oriented economy, the development of independent creative thinking is a key educational priority.

Problem-based learning is a methodology that presents learners with problem-based tasks and research scenarios grounded in scientific knowledge. Such problems emerge within learners' cognitive processes, encouraging objective inquiry and the formulation of logically sound conclusions. A problem situation is defined as a specific mental state of the learner associated with recognising contradictions while performing a task. Awareness of such contradictions generates the need to acquire new knowledge about methods and conditions for completing the task, thereby initiating purposeful cognitive search. It is essential that problem situations correspond to the objectives of knowledge acquisition; they must be accessible to learners, stimulate their cognitive activity, and not be solvable solely on the basis of existing knowledge, while remaining sufficient for independent analysis and identification of unknown elements.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The merits of problem-based learning are manifold. It engenders intellectual engagement and practical application in learners, which are accompanied by positive emotional responses (interest, satisfaction). It is evident that the process in question facilitates the development of intellectual skills, including perception, observation, imagination, analysis, classification, evidence-based reasoning, and others. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that creative abilities are also developed, such as the ability to identify problematic situations, formulate questions, and devise ways to resolve them. In the contemporary educational environment, the role of the teacher has evolved to encompass the responsibility of orchestrating the learning process in a manner that not only fosters reproductive thinking but also encourages creative thinking among learners. In the context of a market economy, the cultivation of independent creative thinking has emerged as a pivotal educational imperative. Problem-based learning can be defined as a methodology in which learning tasks and problem situations are formulated on the basis of scientifically grounded principles. During learners' cognitive processes, contradictions arise that prompt them to engage in objective inquiry and draw logically sound scientific conclusions. A problem situation is defined as a particular mental state of the learner that arises from the discovery of contradictions during the execution of a specific task. The recognition of such a conflict invariably gives rise to the necessity of acquiring new knowledge about the methods and conditions for carrying out the work. This, in turn, initiates a purposeful cognitive search.

CONCLUSION

Problem-based learning has been identified as one of the most significant innovative models in modern education, with a focus on developing students' independent, critical, and creative thinking skills (Smith, 2019). The fundamental objective of this pedagogical approach is to devise problem-based scenarios that motivate students to engage in cognitive exploration, formulate tasks, and develop logically sound solutions. This approach is designed to ensure not only the acquisition of knowledge but also the development of the practical skills necessary for professional practice.

The efficacy of problem-based learning is contingent upon several factors. These include students' preparedness for independent intellectual endeavour, a high level of subject-specific and methodological expertise on the part of the instructor, and the integration of contemporary teaching technologies and information and communication tools. Notwithstanding certain limitations—such as increased demands on student preparation, significant time investment, and the need for highly qualified teachers—problem-based learning has undeniable advantages, including the development of analytical and creative skills, the formation of sustained cognitive motivation, and a positive emotional attitude towards the learning process.

Consequently, problem-based learning is regarded as a promising direction for the modernisation of educational practice. It is argued that this approach is capable of ensuring a qualitative improvement in students' knowledge and skills, as well as their readiness for independent professional and research activities.

References:

1. Tajibay S., Kengesbayevich R.M. (2024). Characteristics of development and socialization of teenagers. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(5), 886–890.
2. Kengesbayevich R.M. (2025). Individual personality traits of junior pupils in schools of education. In: *International Conference on Adaptive Learning Technologies (Vol. 13, pp. 24–25)*.
3. Бурхонова Г.Г., Акрамова Н.М. Повышение профессиональной компетенции современного преподавателя // *Проблемы науки*. – 2019. – № 11-2 (144).
4. Лернер И.Я. *Проблемное обучение*. – М.: Знание, 1974. – 64 с.
5. Махмутов М.И. *Организация проблемного обучения в школе: книга для учителей*. – М.: Просвещение, 1977. – 240 с.
6. Оконь В. *Основы проблемного обучения / пер. с польск.* – М.: Просвещение, 1968. – 208 с.
7. Хуторской А.В. *Дидактическая эвристика: теория и технология креативного обучения*. – М.: Изд-во МГУ, 2003. – 416 с.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №4(4)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.